

“Growth Predictor”: A new predictive modelling and quantitative microbial risk assessment tool

Panagiotis N. Skandamis

Department of Food Science & Human Nutrition, Laboratory of Food Quality Control & Hygiene, Agricultural University of Athens, Iera Odos 75, 118 55 Athens, Greece

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ABSTRACT

A new predictive modelling and quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) software, developed in R, is available on-line (<https://skandamis.shinyapps.io/Microbial-Growth-Predictor-Dashboard/>). Primary model fitting is carried out with the Baranyi model. Secondary fitting and growth simulations are based on gamma models with or without interactions. The same gamma terms can be used for fitting and growth simulations under static or dynamic conditions. One of the novel features is the use of normal distributions to describe the variability in T, pH, a_w , the levels of a single inhibitor and the inter-strain variability in growth limits. The QMRA is comprised of four consecutive modules from primary production until consumption. In addition to prevalence, the modules may also consider partition, mixing and cross-contamination. Variability can be introduced through a variety of probability distributions, for initial contamination, re-contamination, storage time and temperature, product characteristics, serving size and maximum population density. Fixed or variable log reductions during cooking, may be introduced as user-defined values or probability distributions, respectively, or estimated by a Bigelow thermal inactivation model. The trilinear primary growth model is used for estimating log changes, based on μ_{max} obtained by gamma models. The QMRA outputs include graphical distribution of ingested dose and probability of illness (P_{ill}), as well as tabular estimates. The user may select built-in dose-response models, or define the parameters values of exponential, beta-Poisson, beta-binomial and binomial dose-response models. The tool is intended for multiple users from the scientific community, the authorities and the food industry, for growth simulations and high-resolution risk assessments.

1. Introduction

Over the last decades, there has been a shift from empirical quality control and intuitive development of safe food formulations (based on scientific literature) to quality- and safety-by design. This entails the ability to forecast microbial behavior, based on the combination of multiple hurdles, including the intrinsic properties of the food, e.g., pH, a_w , antimicrobial compounds, the gaseous composition of package and the foreseeable storage conditions. Predictive modelling has been a widely accepted methodology for the systematic application of multiple hurdle theory in controlling the growth of pathogens and spoilage organisms in foods.

The use of predictive modelling principles requires a substantial amount of biological and mathematical expertise, and this often discourages end users, such as the food industry or the regulatory authorities, to adopt predictive modelling-based thinking in their daily practice. The development of predictive modelling tools, offering readily available predictions of microbial population dynamics, based on built-

in mathematical models aimed to assist in understanding the benefits of predictive modelling and foster its wide application (Possas et al., 2022). The use of such tools offers the scientific, quantitative basis, required for numerous informed decisions or quantitative assessments, such as: (i) the establishment of shelf life of foods (date marking) based on the expected growth of spoilage and pathogenic organisms, (ii) assessing whether a safety intervention, e.g., thermal process, may deliver the desired log reductions (performance criterion) and meet the performance standards (objectives), (iii) predicting the relative growth or inactivation of microorganisms in two alternative product formulations, which differ in specific levels of variables controlling microbial behavior, or (iv) evaluating whether a food formulation will ensure compliance with microbiological criteria, etc.

Adopting quantitative approaches in food quality and safety increases objectivity and transparency in risk assessments and the confidence of risk managers by substantiating public health decisions on quantitative risk assessment. Furthermore, it provides credibility in product quality and safety in the food trade, among food suppliers, food

E-mail address: pskan@aua.gr.

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business operators (FBOs) and the consumers. A pending challenge is to invent the (software) tools or improve the existing ones in a direction that would facilitate the systematic process of using predictive modelling principles, in making science-based, informed risk management decisions. This becomes more imperative in view of the evolving regulatory framework and the shift from hazard-based to risk-based thinking in food safety (Koutsoumanis & Aspridou, 2016; Messens et al., 2023).

A detailed list of existing predictive modelling and risk assessment tools can be found in the review by Tenenhaus-Aziza and Ellouze (2015), updated by Possas et al. (2022). Most predictive models coded in the existing tools are mathematical equations with pre-defined parameter estimates by the administrators of the software. These estimates are often based on model fitting to non-accessible experimental data, or publicly available models in the published literature. As such, the user cannot easily update the parameters of the included models or introduce new mathematical equations, e.g., for a new hazard or a food matrix that has not already been included in these tools. Unless a software offers the option to introduce new models, through an equation editor, which in most cases, requires some relevant background by the user. However, there are numerous tools that enable the fitting of mathematical models to growth or inactivation datasets (Garre et al., 2023).

A convenient strategy for readily updating models in these tools is to rely on gamma concept-based models (Mejlholm et al., 2010; <http://fssp.food.dtu.dk/>). These models may be easily tailored (calibrated) to different foods or target strains by updating, respectively, the reference μ_{max} of the target organisms in the food of concern, or the cardinal values for growth, such as minimum values of T , pH , a_w or the *Minimum Inhibitory Concentration* of antimicrobials. This type of predictive models is also proposed by the available ISO methods that offer guidance for conducting challenge tests with proper use of cardinal values, for assessing the compliance of foods with the Microbiological Criteria for *Listeria monocytogenes* (ISO 20976-1:2019, n.d.; ISO 23691, 2025).

Next to the predictive modelling capacity of the aforementioned tools, there is remarkable need of their integration in quantitative risk assessment modules, that estimate the levels of ingested pathogens cumulatively from farm to fork. In this context, promising and widely used tools that combine predictive modelling principles with modular risk assessment are available, such as *iRisk* (Chen et al., 2013; <https://irisk.foodrisk.org/>) and *MicroHibro* (González et al., 2019; <http://microhibro.com/>). However, understanding the mathematical and statistical background of the QMRA modules of such tools, still requires substantial relevant background by the user, while it is difficult to track the link between the outputs and the inputs, or to assess the sensitivity of the outcomes against changes of inputs in real-time. Furthermore, strain-to-strain variability, which undoubtedly impacts the risk assessment outputs (Aryani et al., 2015; den Besten et al., 2017; Lianou & Koutsoumanis, 2011) cannot be explicitly reflected in the existing tools. Collectively, these limitations, although they only relate to practicality and not scientific rigor of the available software applications, discourage the routine use of such tools by the candidate end-users, including FBOs, researchers, and risk managers. As such, there is still work to do to establish the systematic use of predictive modelling by decision makers. Easiness in use, improvements in visualization and tabulation of outputs, active engagement of the user and interactivity are key issues to resolve this challenge.

A new web-based software tool developed in R (<https://skandamis.shinyapps.io/Microbial-Growth-Predictor-Dashboard/>) is introduced that can be used for fitting models and performing growth simulations, as well as for conducting QMRA. The predictive modelling module of the proposed freeware is based on the systematic application of gamma concept-based models, with or without interaction. The user-dependent option to exclude the interaction term “ ξ ” of the gamma concept, was

deemed appropriate because the mathematical formulas used to estimate the value of this term have not been explicitly verified for other microorganisms than *L. monocytogenes* and proteolytic *Clostridium botulinum* (Koukou et al., 2021; Le Marc et al., 2002; Mejlholm et al., 2010). Growth simulations are based on user-defined or built-in growth limiting values of T , pH , a_w and the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of up to 6 inhibitors. Furthermore, the tool also offers primary and secondary (gamma) model fitting modules. Notably, the user is amenable to select among various gamma terms both for secondary model fitting and growth simulations. The application is also capable of modelling the inter-strain variability under static or dynamic conditions, by introducing the growth limits (=‘cardinal values’) of the target organism as normal distributions $N(\bar{x}, SD)$. Finally, the gamma-based growth models are integrated into a modular quantitative microbial risk assessment, with built-in as well as user-defined dose-response models, i.e., defining parameter values in built-in equations. All features are available in a web-based environment, with real-time update of outputs in response to changes in deterministic or stochastic inputs.

2. General overview of the tool

The following modules are available in *Growth Predictor*: (1) “*User-defined conditions*” (the default page of the software as shown in Fig. 1), where the user may simulate microbial growth of any microorganism, deterministically or stochastically, i.e., via probability distributions of product characteristics or temperature, sampled with *Monte Carlo* simulation for user-defined number of iterations (Table 1). Simulations may refer to under isothermal (static) or non-isothermal (dynamic) conditions, with user-defined cardinal values of T , pH , a_w and up to six inhibitors, most of them introduced either as single values (deterministically), normal distributions, or selected from a built-in database of cardinal values for different microorganism, embedded in the tool (Table 1). When selecting cardinal values from the built-in database, there is still the option to describe the inter-strain variability in the cardinal values of the organism, by typing the standard deviation (SD) of the normal distribution describing the cardinal values, since this information is not included in the data-base (*dbase*). The lag time can also be introduced deterministically or stochastically as normal distribution of the *Work-to-be-done* (*ho*). The model outputs can be downloaded in an .xls format (Excel) file and saved on a local disc, (2) *Modular process model*: this is a modular Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) model, where the food chain, from primary production till the consumer, is split in four stages, namely “*Farm to end of processing*”, “*End of processing to retail*”, “*Retail*” and “*Domestic storage*”. The user may introduce deterministically or stochastically the storage time and temperature, contamination or re-contamination levels of a pathogen, the reduction due to cooking or processing, the product characteristics (pH , a_w and only one *inhibitor*), the corresponding cardinal values of the target pathogen and the serving size (Table 1). The impact of additional inhibitors may be indirectly described via calculating the proper μ_{ref} value in the presence of the inhibitors, based on the “*User-defined conditions*” tab. The final output based on these inputs is a distribution of dose at consumption and the log of Probability of illness, according to the user-defined prevalence and serving size. The user may provide parameter values for different built-in dose response equations or select one of the following published and built-in dose-response models: (i) *Listeria monocytogenes* model for Ready-To-Eat foods (Chen et al., 2013; FAO/WHO, 2004) for susceptible population, (ii) the same model for non-susceptible population and (iii) STEC model for ground beef hamburgers (Cassin et al., 1998) and (iv) *Salmonella* model for eggs and broiler chickens. The numerical QMRA outputs include the average probability of illness per serving (P_{III}) and the expected (predicted)

Fig. 1. Starting page of “User defined simulation module” of the software tool. Shaded areas illustrate growth variability due to variability in storage temperature ($T \sim Normal[8,0.6]$) and uncertainty of lag time ($h_0 \sim Normal[2,0.7]$) for 1000 iterations. The cardinal values for microbial growth are the default values of the tool.

number of annual cases, after setting the total number of annual servings. All model outputs can be downloaded in an .xls format file and saved on the hard disc at a path specified by the user. (3) *Fitting primary models and secondary gamma models* to estimate cardinal values for growth.

3. Module “Primary model fitting”

This module is used to fit the analytical (explicit) version of the Baranyi primary model (Eqs. 1 & 2; Baranyi & Roberts, 1994) to user-uploaded datasets describing the changes in Log_{10} CFU/g or ml (dependent variable) of a microorganism as a function of time. The necessary transformations of population density from Log_{10} to Ln scale are performed at the back end of the tool for fitting the model according to Eq. 1. The model contains four parameters with time as the single independent variable.

$$\ln(N_t) = \ln(N_0) + \mu_{max}A(t) - \frac{1}{m} \ln\left(1 + \frac{\exp[m\mu_{max}A(t)] - 1}{\exp\{m[\ln(N_{max}) - \ln(N_0)]\}}\right) \quad (1)$$

$$A(t) = t + \frac{1}{\nu} \ln\left(\frac{\exp(-\nu t) + q_0}{1 + q_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } \nu = \mu_{max} \& q_0 = \frac{P_0}{K_p} = \frac{1}{\exp(h_0) - 1} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{lag} = \lambda = \frac{h_0}{\mu_{max}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } h_0 = \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{q_0}\right) \quad (5)$$

A representative graphical output of fitting a growth curve with the above model is shown in Fig. 2.

4. Module “Estimation of cardinal values”

This module can fit a gamma model comprised of one to five gamma terms accounting for the impact of temperature, pH, a_w and two inhibitors, to a uni- or multivariate data set uploaded by the user.

$$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} \cdot \gamma(T) \cdot \gamma(pH) \cdot \gamma(a_w) \cdot \gamma(\text{inhibitor 1}) \cdot \gamma(\text{inhibitor 2}) \cdot \gamma(\text{inhibitor 3}) \quad (6)$$

where μ_{max} is the maximum specific growth rate (1/time) and μ_{opt} is the μ_{max} at optimal conditions.

For temperature, one of the following two gamma terms may be selected for fitting:

(1) The (linear) square-root model:

$$\left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{ref} - T_{min}}\right)^2 \quad (7)$$

where T is temperature ($^{\circ}C$), T_{min} is the theoretical minimum temperature allowing growth and T_{ref} ($^{\circ}C$) is the reference temperature at which, the value of μ_{max} (1/time) equals to μ_{ref} . The value of μ_{ref} is determined experimentally at the optimal levels of the remaining conditions, or at levels that do not pose any additional inhibitory effect other than that of temperature.

(2) The cardinal model by Rosso et al. (1995), with $n = 2$:

Table 1
Probability distributions used in “Growth Predictor” for the input variables. Boldface letters indicate variables that can be introduced stochastically in both growth simulation and QMRA modules (using the boldface probability distribution types).

Growth simulations	QMRA	Variable	Available (variability) distributions	Parameters
	√	Initial population or recontamination (N _o)	Normal ^a	Mean SD
	√		Pert	Min Mode Max
			Discrete	Manual typing/ pasting values to a X vector (No) vs a P vector (Probability of occurrence)
√	√	Temperature (°C)	Normal	Mean SD
	√		Logistic	Alpha Beta
	√		Gamma	Alpha Beta
	√		Pert	Min Mode Max
			Uniform	Min Max
			Discrete	Manual typing/ pasting values to a X vector (T) vs a P vector (Probability of occurrence)
			Dynamic profile	Upload an XL file with two columns (time/T). Available only for modules 2 and 3
√	√	pH	Normal	Mean SD
√	√	a_w	Normal	Mean SD
√	√	Inhibitor (only one)	Normal	Mean SD
√	√	Time (days)	Normal	Mean SD
	√		Exponential	1/mean ^b Max time

Table 1 (continued)

Growth simulations	QMRA	Variable	Available (variability) distributions	Parameters
	√		Logistic	Alpha Beta
	√		Gamma	Alpha Beta
			Triangular	Min Middle Max
	√		Pert	Min Mode Max
	√	Maximum population density (N _{max})	Normal	Mean SD
	√		Uniform	Min Max
	√	Reduction (e.g., due to cooking or nonthermal inactivation)	Normal	Mean SD
	√		Pert	Min Mode Max
	√		Uniform	Min Max
	√		Estimated by a Bigelow inactivation model with D _{ref} , Z values as fixed values & time, T as fixed values or normal distributions. Available for the domestic module. Chardon & Evers, 2017	Mean time SD time Mean T SD T
√	√	Cardinal values of microbial growth: T, pH, a _w , MIC of inhibitor	Normal	Mean SD
	√	Serving size (g)	Normal	Mean SD
	√		Gamma	Alpha Beta

^a : values of mean and SD are introduced at log₁₀ scale.

^b : mean is the user input.

Fig. 2. Typical output of “primary model fitting” module. Refer to “Primary_Model_fitting_Time_LogN.xlsx” of the Supplementary material.

$$\begin{cases} 0, & X \leq X_{min} \\ \frac{(X - X_{max})(X - X_{min})^n}{(X_{opt} - X_{min})^{n-1} \{ (X_{opt} - X_{min})(X - X_{opt}) - (X_{opt} - X_{max})[(n-1)X_{opt} + X_{min} - nX] \}}, & X_{min} < X < X_{max} \\ 0, & X \geq X_{max} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where, in addition to the parameter T_{min} of Eq. 7, the following two parameters are included: T_{max} (°C), the (theoretical) maximum temperature allowing growth and T_{opt} (°C) the (theoretical) optimum temperature for growth.

where pH_{min} is the (theoretical) minimum temperature allowing growth.

Similarly, for pH, the next three gamma terms are available:

(2) The cardinal model by Rosso et al. (1995), with $n = 1$:

$$\begin{cases} 0, & pH \leq pH_{min} \\ \frac{(pH - pH_{max})(pH - pH_{min})}{(pH_{opt} - pH_{min})(pH - pH_{opt}) - (pH_{opt} - pH_{max})(pH_{min} - pH)}, & pH_{min} < pH < pH_{max} \\ 0, & pH \geq pH_{max} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

(1) The linear term introduced by Presser et al. (1997):

where, in addition to the parameter pH_{min} of Eq. 9, the following two parameters are included: pH_{max} , the (theoretical) maximum pH allowing growth and pH_{opt} , the (theoretical) optimum pH for growth.

$$1 - 10^{(pH_{min} - pH)} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3. Representative fittings of different secondary gamma terms to experimental data: (a) Rosso cardinal model (Eq. 8) for temperature (Rosso et al., 1995), (b) pH term of Eq. 9, acc. to Presser et al. (1997), (c) pH term of Eq. 11 based on Aryani et al. (2015), (d) and (e) gamma term for the effect of two inhibitors, singly, according to Eq. 13. Blue points represent the observed data, green points the corresponding predicted values and the red line represents the continuous fitted line of the model. Refer to the relevant .xls (Excel) files of Supplementary material. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2
Representative examples of software numerical outputs when fitting single secondary gamma terms for temperature, pH, a_w and inhibitor.

Variable	Gamma term	Parameter	Parameter estimates (value \pm SE)	Goodness-of-fit criteria		
				RMSE	AIC	BIC
T	Eq. 3 (Rosso et al., 1995)	μ_{opt}	1.313 \pm 0.0292	0.0602	-65.133	-58.654
		T_{min}	0.92 \pm 1.41			
		T_{opt}	35.6 \pm 0.3			
		T_{max}	43.0 \pm 0.1			
pH	Eq. 4 (Presser et al., 1997)	μ_{opt}	2.060 \pm 0.039	0.0907	-15.596	-14.402
		pH_{min}	4.68 \pm 0.02			
pH	Eq. 6	μ_{opt}	2.13 \pm 0.06	0.0946	-14.547	-12.607
		$pH_{1/2}$	5.15 \pm 0.04			
		pH_{min}	4.69 \pm 0.03			
Inhibitor	Eq. 8	μ_{opt}	1.230 \pm 0.022	0.022	-28.39	-27.993
		MIC	30.720 \pm 1.899			
		n1	1.36 \pm 0.230			
		n2	1.09 \pm 0.316			
	Eq. 8	μ_{opt}	1.855 \pm 0.065	0.0835	-26.042	-22.951
		MIC	12.168 \pm 0.578			
		n1	0.39 \pm 0.03			
		n2	Fixed at 1			

(3) The model introduced by Aryani et al. (2015):

$$1 - 2^{\frac{(pH - pH_{min})}{(pH_{min} - pH_{1/2})}} \quad (11)$$

where $pH_{1/2}$ is the pH at which μ_{max} equals to the 50 % of μ_{opt} .

To describe the effect of a_w , the user may select among the two following gamma terms:

(1) The linear term:

$$\frac{a_w - a_{w\ min}}{1 - a_{w\ min}} \quad (12)$$

where $a_{w\ min}$ is the (theoretical) minimum a_w allowing growth.

(2) The cardinal model by Rosso et al. (1995), with $n = 2$,

where, in addition to the parameter $a_{w\ min}$ of Eq. 12, the following two parameters are included: $a_{w\ max}$, the (theoretical) maximum a_w allowing growth and $a_{w\ opt}$, the (theoretical) optimum a_w for growth.

The following gamma term is used to describe the impact of each inhibitor (Koukou et al., 2021):

$$\left[1 - \left(\frac{C_i}{MIC_i} \right)^{n1} \right]^{n2} \quad (13)$$

where c_i is the concentration of the inhibitor (e.g., mg/L, ppm, mM, or else) and MIC the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of the same inhibitor. For organic acids, MIC refers to the undissociated form of the acid, which is the most active antimicrobial fraction. The units are up to the user, but they should be selected consistently with the inputs of c_i . The parameters n_1 and n_2 are exponents that define the shape of the curve illustrating the dependence of μ_{max} on the concentration of the inhibitor (c_i).

Typical examples of fitted univariate gamma models to experimental data for T, pH, or an inhibitor are shown in Fig. 3 and the parameter estimates in Table 2. When more than one variable is fitted, in parallel to displaying the fitted model outputs, the central graph is updated with

the predicted data points and four additional simulation (continuous) lines of μ_{max} in response to the whole range of the pre-selected independent variable. Each simulation line corresponds to a fixed value of the concomitant non-displayed variable(s), at the 25, 50 and 75 and 100 % intervals of their range used for model fitting.

5. Module “User defined conditions”: growth simulations with gamma models

The user-input form of this module is shown in Fig. 4. Growth simulations are based on the levels of intrinsic factors of the foods (pH, a_w and inhibitors), the storage and packaging conditions (extrinsic factors), and time, according to the “multiple hurdle theory”. The parameters of these gamma terms represent the growth limiting conditions (or cardinal values) of each factor, such as T_{min} , T_{max} , pH_{min} , a_{wmin} , MIC, etc. The impact of a_w is considered per se, independently of the humectant used for a_w adjustment. Likewise, the pH terms refer to the pure impact of protons, whereas the impact of the undissociated fraction of organic acids is described with separate terms of Eq. 13, in the total gamma expression of Eq. 6.

The default secondary model used to estimate the μ_{max} is the following gamma model with or without interactions (ξ) (a user-enabled option), including terms for T, pH, a_w , and one inhibitor, e.g., nitrite (then by default, $n1 = 1$ and $n2 = 2$) (Mejlholm et al., 2010):

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{max} &= \mu_{ref} \left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{ref} - T_{min}} \right)^2 (1 - 10^{pH_{min} - pH}) \left(\frac{a_w - a_{w\ min}}{1 - a_{w\ min}} \right) \left[1 - \left(\frac{C_i}{MIC} \right)^{n1} \right]^{n2} = \\ &= \mu_{max\ ref} \left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{ref} - T_{min}} \right)^2 (1 - 10^{pH_{min} - pH}) \left(\frac{a_w - a_{wmin}}{1 - a_{wmin}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{NO_2}{MIC} \right)^2 \xi \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

To calculate the interaction term ξ , the following equations are used:

$$\xi = \begin{cases} 1, & \psi \leq 0.5 \\ 2(1 - \psi), & 0.5 < \psi < 1 \\ 0, & \psi \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The screenshot shows the 'User-defined conditions' module interface. It is divided into several sections:

- Static vs Dynamic conditions:** A dropdown menu set to 'Isothermal'. A callout box points to this section with the text: 'Tab for defining the heat inactivation step after growth'.
- Time units:** Radio buttons for 'Days' (selected) and 'Hours'. A callout box points to this section with the text: 'Tab for setting the cardinal values for the secondary'.
- SD of Temp. distr., SD of pH. distr., SD of Inhibitor1 distr.:** Input fields with values 0.25, 0, and 0 respectively. A callout box points to these fields with the text: 'Selecting isothermal/non-isothermal conditions (at this tab)'.
- SD of Time distr., SD of aw distr.:** Input fields with values 0 and 0.003 respectively.
- Num. of iterations:** Input field with value 1000.
- Storage T°C:** A slider ranging from 0 to 65, with a value of 4 selected.
- Storage time (days):** A slider ranging from 0 to 95, with a value of 30 selected.
- pH:** A slider ranging from 3 to 7.5, with a value of 5.31 selected.
- aw:** A slider ranging from 0.88 to 1, with a value of 0.97 selected.
- Inhibitor 1 (% ppm, mM...):** A slider ranging from 0 to 400, with a value of 25 selected.
- Add more inhibitors:** A button.
- Initial contamination (Log CFU/g or ml):** Input field with value 0.
- Maximum population density (Log CFU/g or ml):** Input field with value 2.5.
- Work-To-Be-Done (h0: 0.1 to infinity):** Input field with value 0.01.
- sd ho (stochastic lag):** Input field with value 0.

Callout boxes on the right side of the interface provide further details:

- An orange box contains the text: 'Setting the time and the independent variables controlling microbial growth. 1. Temperature, pH, aw, inhibitor and time can also be introduced as normal distributions 2. Defining the number of iterations to be considered when any of the variables is introduced stochastically as normal distribution (i.e., SD>0) 3. "Add more inhibitors", enables the addition of values for 5 more inhibitors (phenolics, CO₂, organic acids, etc.)'
- A blue box contains the text: 'Setting the initial and maximum (at stationary phase) contamination level'.
- A blue box contains the text: 'Setting the lag time properties'.

Fig. 4. Main side panel of "User-defined conditions" module.

$$\phi(OA_1, OA_2, \dots, OA_i) = (1 - OA_1term \times OA_2term \times \dots \times OA_i term)^2 = \left\{ 1 - \left[\left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{OA_{U,1}}{MIC_{U,1}}} \right) \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{OA_{U,2}}{MIC_{U,2}}} \right) \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{OA_{U,3}}{MIC_{U,3}}} \right) \dots \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{OA_{U,i}}{MIC_{U,i}}} \right) \right] \right\}^2 \quad (21)$$

where, $\psi = \sum_i \frac{\phi_{e_i}}{2 \prod_{j \neq i} (1 - \phi_{e_j})}$

$$\phi(T) = \left[1 - \left(\frac{T - T_{min}}{T_{ref} - T_{min}} \right) \right]^2 \quad (16) \quad (17)$$

$$\phi(a_w) = \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{a_w - a_{w \min}}{a_{w \text{opt}} - a_{w \min}}}\right)^2 \text{ default } a_{w \text{opt}} \text{ is set at } 1 \quad (18)$$

$$\phi(\text{pH}) = \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - 10^{pH_{\min} - \text{pH}}}\right)^2 \quad (19)$$

$$\phi(c_i) = \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{NO_2}{MIC_i}}\right)^2 \quad (20)$$

Eq. 20 applies by default to nitrite, but can be extended to CO_2 (or O_2), phenolic compounds and organic acids or their salts, when they are selected as additional inhibitors, as explained below. When a mixture of organic acids is used their contribution to interaction is expressed via the following equation:

for the mixture of organic acids, applicable when additional inhibitors are selected. The formula of Eq. 21 suggests that the organic acid term also depends on the shape of each organic acid term (OA_i term),

according to Eq. 13.

- C_i : is the concentration of the inhibitor in *ppm*, *mM* or else. The user may choose to enter the concentration in the water phase or the total in food. Care should be taken for consistency with the conditions, which were used for estimation of μ_{ref} , experimentally.
- MIC : is the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (in units considered by the user) of an inhibitor. In the case of organic acids, the MIC refers to the concentration of the undissociated fraction.
- T_{ref} is the reference temperature, at which, the μ_{ref} has been calculated. When Rosso model is selected for the temperature gamma term, T_{ref} becomes T_{opt} and μ_{ref} equals to μ_{opt} .

The gamma terms of Eq. 14 for T , pH and a_w , may be switched to any of the eqs. 8 to 12. Up to six inhibitors (expressed in units defined by the user) can be used in the secondary model of Eq. 14, accounting for the combined effect of the most commonly used inhibitors that could be added in foods formulation, including the role of CO_2 or O_2 in the packaging atmosphere. Nitrite is considered the default inhibitor. The

Fig. 5. Simulated growth with 1000 iterations, based on the gamma model of Eq. 14 with interactions, at 8.6 °C, pH 6, a_w 0.970 and no inhibitors, where T_{\min} follows a normal distribution with mean -0.92 °C and SD 0.8 °C and pH_{\min} follows another normal distribution with average 4.4 and SD 0.25. The remaining cardinal values are the default ones by the tool. H_0 was also considered to follow a normal distribution with average 2.5 and SD 0.5.

1st of the extra inhibitors could be the concentration of CO₂ or O₂ dissolved in the product. The 2nd inhibitor is the concentration of phenolic compounds deposited on product surfaces, associated with smoking processes, e.g., in smoked RTE meats and seafood. The 3rd and 4th inhibitors could represent the concentration of undissociated fractions of lactic, or acetate acid, respectively. Alternative the 3rd inhibitor could represent the concentration of undissociated citric acid and the 4th inhibitor could represent the concentration of undissociated lactic or acetic acid. The 5th inhibitor represents the concentration of undissociated sorbic and benzoic acid. The user may ignore the proposed nomenclature and consider other substitutes for each of the inhibitors. The gamma term conveying the impact each inhibitor in the full model is the one represented by Eq. 13, which requires user input for MIC_i and the two exponents n₁, n₂.

The default values for μ_{ref} refer to a product without inhibitors (c_i = 0 for all six of them). To estimate the μ_{ref} in a food formulated with multiple inhibitors (Prod_{ref}), first set the values of the inhibitors and use 25 °C (i.e., the default value), or a new (user-defined) temperature as T_{ref}. Then, the newly calculated μ_{max} that appears on top of the graphical output, equals the μ_{ref} of the new reference product (Prod_{ref}) at the selected T_{ref}. The new value of μ_{ref} should replace the old one at the ‘cardinal values’ tab. Switching back all inhibitors to 0, the predicted μ_{max} equals the new μ_{ref}. Hereafter, any value of the inhibitors greater than 0 would represent the extra amounts of inhibitors added to the reference product (Prod_{ref}).

Table 3

Representative dataset for growth simulation under dynamic conditions of T, pH and a_w. Shaded cell indicate the shortest time interval of the profile, which should be used for efficiently selecting the interpolation step, i.e., a value lower than this interval.

hours	T	pH	aw
0	10	6.25	0.98
6	8	6.25	0.98
22	6	6.035	0.98
29	9	6.035	0.98
46	5.3	5.935	0.95
53	7.4	5.935	0.95
69	9	5.685	0.95
78	8.1	5.685	0.95
99	6.2	5.615	0.93
117	5	5.615	0.93
128	10	5.615	0.93
140	10	5.06	0.93
...

For growth simulation, the differential equations of the Baranyi primary model (Baranyi et al., 1995; Baranyi & Roberts, 1994) is used, based on user-defined “initial contamination (Log CFU/g or ml)”, “Maximum population density (Log CFU/g or ml)” and the “Work-to-be-done” parameter (h₀) that reflects the lag time (λ) of the organism. The mathematical form of the growth model used is:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{q_t}{q_t + 1} \mu_{max} \left(1 - \left(\frac{N_t}{N_{max}} \right)^m \right) N_t, \text{ where } q_t = \frac{P_t}{K_p} \tag{22}$$

$$h_0 = \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_0} \right) = -\ln(a_0) = \mu_{max} \lambda \tag{23}$$

where q_t is the physiological state of the microorganism, that depends on the cell ‘history’ inherited from their previous environments. It is defined as the ratio of a per cell critical product (P_t) that needs to be produced by the organism to exit the lag phase and the Michaelis-Menten constant K_p. P_t follows Monod kinetics. The variable a₀ represents the percentage of cells in the new environment that continue to grow with the μ_{max} of the previous environment, i.e., without being affected by the shift to the new environment. As such, a₀ equal to 0 suggests no growth and 1, suggests no lag. The shape parameter m that determines the curvature of the transition from exponential to stationary phase is set at 1 (no curvature).

The lag time depends on h₀ and μ_{max} according to Eq. 5, which represents the work-to-be-done by the microorganism to exit the lag phase. The default value for h₀ in the tool is the lowest acceptable one, i.

Fig. 6. Growth simulation based on the gamma model **without** interactions, under dynamic (non-isothermal) conditions at pH 6.56, a_w 0.97, 25 ppm of inhibitor 1 (the rest are 0) and μ_{ref} 0.419 h^{-1} at T_{ref} $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The shaded area represents the prediction range, considering variability (200 iterations) in h_0 and the cardinal values, herein only T_{min} by selecting “Normal dist.” from the drop-down list of “cardinal” tab. T_{min} follows a normal distribution with average $-0.92 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and SD 0.5, and h_0 follows a normal distribution with average 0.2 and SD 0.6. The remaining model inputs maintain the default values of the tool. The limits of the shaded area represent the 5 (●), 50 (median; ●) and 95 % percentile (●) of the resulting distribution of Log CFU/g. *Interpolation step* = 0.5. Refer to file “Time-T.xlsx” of Supplementary material.

e., 0.01, whereas it can receive values up to infinity. The higher the value of h_0 , the longer the lag time. The parameter h_0 can be also introduced as normal distribution with h_0 as mean value and SD defined by the user in the last box of the Int/Extrinsic factors (on the lefthand side below the sliders of the input variables – see below).

Eqs. 22 and 23 are solved numerically with the *Rung-Kutta 4* method. The μ_{max} at the user-defined conditions of T , pH , a_w and the levels of up to six *inhibitors*, is calculated by the gamma-type secondary model of Eq. 1. If the “Rosso model” is selected (in the “Cardinal values” tab), the temperature term of Eq. 7 in the gamma expression (Eq. 14) is replaced by that of Eq. 8 for $n = 2$. In this case, T_{ref} therein represents T_{opt} and μ_{ref} becomes μ_{opt} . Likewise, when the “ $pH_{1/2}$ ” model is selected (can be co-selected with the Rosso cardinal models for other terms), the gamma term for pH in Eq. 14 is replaced by that of Eq. 11 (Aryani et al., 2015). The user may select simulation time in days or hours. The same requirement holds also for dynamic conditions, as detailed further down in the manuscript.

6. Cardinal values reflecting strain-variability

The variability in the growth limits among strains leads to substantial variability in prediction of time needed for certain log increase by all possible strains that may contaminate a food (Aryani et al., 2015; Lianou & Koutsoumanis, 2011). As such, it plays a key role in the assessment of consumers’ exposure to the actual concentration of a hazard in a food and underlines the need to reassess the way that growth simulations are carried out in the QMRA framework. Gamma models are the most suitable model category to reflect strain-to-strain variability in growth predictions, because it offers the option to introduce the growth limits of gamma terms, as probability distributions (Fig. 5).

In “Growth Predictor”, apart from assigning a single value, the cardinal values for the minimum T , pH , a_w , and the *Minimum Inhibitory Concentration-MIC* of one inhibitor can be introduced as normal distributions with mean and SD defined in the proper numeric input boxes, or they can be directly extracted by a built-in database. Stochastic cardinal

Fig. 7. Growth simulation based on the gamma model **with** interactions, under dynamic (non-isothermal) conditions with default values of μ_{ref} 0.419 h^{-1} at T_{ref} $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and all inhibitors set to 0, except for *phenolics*, which are set to 5 ppm. The shaded area represents the prediction range, considering variability (200 iterations) in h_o and the cardinal values, herein only T_{min} by selecting “Normal dist.” from the drop-down list of “cardinal” tab. T_{min} follows a normal distribution with average $-0.92 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and SD 0.5, and h_o follows a normal distribution with average 0.2 and SD 0.6. The limits of the shaded area represent the 5 (●), 50 (median; ●) and 95 % percentile (●) of the resulting distribution of Log CFU/g. *Interpolation step* = 0.2. Refer to file “Time-T-pH-aw.xlsx” of Supplementary material.

values may reflect inter-strain variability in the growth limits. Growth simulation under variable conditions (T , pH , a_w and inhibitor), as well as time and cardinal values is performed with *Monte Carlo* (MC) simulation for user-defined number of iterations.

7. Growth simulations under dynamic conditions

Simulation under dynamic conditions can be carried out by selecting “Dynamic t-T” for dynamic T profile, or “Dynamic-t-T/pH/ a_w ”, for dynamic T - pH - a_w datasets. The “*Interpolation time step*” is dependent on the time intervals of the imported dataset and should not equal, neither exceed the minimum time step observed in the imported (*time-T*, or *time-T-pH- a_w*) data. For example, in the dataset of Table 3, the minimum time step is detected between the first two measurements, i.e., 6 h. In this case, the allowed interpolation step should be less than 6. However, the minimum distance between two consecutive time points may not be the interval between the first two values of time in the imported dataset. In principle, the interpolation step aims to increase the interpolated values

between the consecutive levels of T , pH and a_w imported by the user. Therefore, the optimal interpolation step is dependent on the dynamic dataset and needs to be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

Once the user selects the type of dynamic data set, then the proper box prompts the user to upload a dynamic data set by locating the file to be uploaded on the PC (“Browse” button). Once the dynamic dataset is uploaded the growth curve is updated by showing the Log N vs time along with the recorded values of T (*Dynamic time-T file*, Fig. 6), or T , pH and a_w (*Dynamic time-T/pH/ a_w file*, Fig. 7). The remaining functions, i. e., stochastic growth limits or adjusting the h_o with or without SD remain as pre-selected. Furthermore, the user may still adjust the constant value of the other inhibitors 1 to 6, via the sliders, as explained above.

8. Tab “Module”: appending a heating step after storage

This tab offers the option of applying a heating step at the end of growth simulation. The log reductions caused by heating are calculated

Fig. 8. The dynamic growth simulation of Fig. 6, followed by a heating step at 58 °C for 14 min, with $D_{ref} = 38$ min, $T_{ref} = 54$ °C and $Z = 7$ °C. The colored dots represent the downshifts of LogN due to heating, corresponding to the 5 (●), 50 (median; ●) and 95 % percentile (●) of the prediction range by the end of storage, which encompasses the variability in T_{min} and h_0 .

based on the duration of the heating process (=heating time), the heating temperature, the D -value (D_{ref}) of the target organism at a reference temperature (T_{ref}) and the associated Z value, which describes the dependency of the D -value on temperature. The inclusion or exclusion of the heating step are controlled by interchangeably clicking the relevant “Growth & Inactivation” and “Growth” radio buttons. The log reductions ($LogR$) are calculated by the Bigelow model converting the cooking time ($time$) at a specified temperature (T) to an equivalent time at a reference temperature (T_{ref}). The following equations are used in the calculations:

$$LogR = \frac{time}{D_T} \quad (24)$$

where D_T is the D -value at the cooking temperature T . It is estimated as a function of the D value at the T_{ref} , i.e., D_{ref} , and the Z value, i.e., the temperature change that causes a 10-fold change in the D -value, based on the following equation:

$$D_T = D_{ref} \cdot 10^{\frac{T_{ref}-T}{Z}} \quad (25)$$

The module is applicable to both static or dynamic growth simulations preceding the heat inactivation and for any options of

deterministically or stochastically introduced cardinal values. A typical example of simulating thermal inactivation, following the non-isothermal growth of Fig. 6 is illustrated in Fig. 8.

9. Module “Modular Process Risk model”

The model is comprised of four modules, namely: (i) *Farm to end of processing*, (ii) *Processing to retail*, (iii) *Retail* and (iv) *Domestic storage*. The screen is split into two independently scrolling parts (Fig. 9). The left panel lists the model input variables from top to bottom and the right panel shows the model output distribution, i.e., the dose at the time of consumption and the probability distribution of the logarithm of probability of illness.

The input variables are the initial contamination or re-contamination (e.g., due to cross-contamination), the storage conditions, the product intrinsic properties (T , pH , a_w and one Inhibitor), the work-to-be-done (h_0) parameter associated with the lag time, the microorganism-specific cardinal values and the Log reduction due to processing or cooking. The following variables can be introduced deterministically or stochastically, by selecting the type and parameters of specific distributions (normal, logistic, gamma, exponential, uniform or Pert), the list

Fig. 9. Generic output of the “Modular process model” module that shows the two independent scrolling windows for the input and output distributions, respectively, including the distribution of the serving size.

Table 4
List of dose-response models available in *Growth Predictor*.

Model	Microorganism	Formula	Parameters	Reference
Exponential	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> , susceptible population (elder, >60 years old)	$P = 1 - e^{-r \times Dose}$	$r = 8.39e-12$	Chen et al., 2013; FAO/WHO, 2004; Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2017
	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> , non-susceptible population		$r = 5.34e-14$	
	Also available as user-defined model			r : user-defined
Beta-Poisson	<i>Salmonella</i> in eggs and broiler meat	$P = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{SF \times Dose}{\beta}\right)^{-\alpha}$	SF: scaling factor (1 by default) $B \sim \text{Triangular}(38.49, 57.69, 51.45)$ $\alpha \sim \text{Triangular}(0.0763, 0.2274, 0.1324)$	FAO/WHO, 2002
	Also available as user-defined model	$P = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{Dose}{\beta}\right)^{-\alpha}$	α, β : user-defined	Strachan et al., 2005
Beta-Binomial	STEC in ground beef	$P = 1 - (1 - P_i(1))^{Dose}$	$P_i(1) \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ $\alpha = 0.267$ $\ln \beta \sim N(5.435, 2.47)$ or α, β : user-defined, as parameters of Beta distribution	Cassin et al., 1998
	Also available as user-defined model		$P_i(1) = r$: user-defined	This tool
Binomial	Available only as user-defined model	$P = 1 - (1 - P_i(1))^{Dose}$		This tool

varying with the input-variable as described in Table 1:

- Initial contamination (for the module “From Farm to end of processing”), or re-contamination (N_0), due to cross-contamination, at each of the vertical modules 2–4
- Storage time
- Storage temperature
- Product characteristics (pH, a_w and the level of one inhibitor)
- Final population density (N_{max})
- Log reduction or Log increase (if growth is not calculated via a growth model)
- The cardinal values as in the other two Modules, except for the deterministic input of T_{ref} . The cardinal values can be introduced as fixed values, normal distribution or selected from the built-in dbase of the tool.
- The serving size

Growth in each of the four modules may be calculated based on the gamma growth model (Eq. 1) with or without the interaction term “ ξ ” (Eqs. 2–7), in response to the above input variables or as a user-defined log increase (or log reduction) following a normal distribution with user-defined SD. The user may select or de-select the inclusion of the interaction term “ ξ ”, by the relevant checkbox on the top right box. Growth is simulated based on the trilinear model (Buchanan et al., 1997). Lag time is calculated by Eq. 4, based on the user-defined h_0 and the estimated of μ_{max} , by the gamma model of Eq. 14, for given product characteristics, time and temperature at each module.

The population of the hazard is assumed to be randomly distributed in a serving size, thereby approximating a Poisson distribution (\sim Poisson (N)), where N is the product of the cumulative microbial level (initial contamination + cross contamination + growth) at the time of consumption with the serving size. When a lethal treatment is applied at the first module, or cooking is applied before consumption, the surviving, Poisson distributed populations in the two modules (i.e., right after processing and in the serving intended for consumption, respectively), follows a binomial distribution:

$$\text{Binomial}(\text{Poisson}(N), 10^{-\text{Log Reductions}}) \quad (26)$$

The above distribution at very high population levels and high log reductions (i.e., very low p of the Binomial distribution) approximates the Poisson distribution. In the output window, the user can set the number of iterations and choose among dose and probability of illness (P_{ill}), through the drop-down of “Select plot” box. When selecting the “Probability of illness”, the user is prompted to define the prevalence and serving size and select one of the built-in dose-response models or a user-defined Exponential, Binomial and Beta Binomial dose-response model (Table 4). The built-in models include two for *L. monocytogenes* (susceptible and non-susceptible individuals), one for *Salmonella* and one for STEC. The latter considers both the variability of consumers susceptibility to the hazard, expressed as probability of illness by a single cell, and the associated uncertainty, expressed as probability distribution of the parameters describing the variability of consumer susceptibility. This entails a significantly higher computation time to deliver the probability of illness when simulating this model. When selecting a user-defined dose-response model, the user needs also to introduce the relevant parameters of the model. The list of built-in dose-response models is regularly expanded by the administrator.

The tool offers the option to resample from the original input distributions, i.e., as a new simulation and update the output. Apart from the distributions of exposing dose and the \log_{10} value of probability of illness, the software provides tabular outputs, including the average, 5, 50 and 95 % percentiles of the dose at the time of consumption and the logarithm of the probability of illness. The predicted average of annual cases are also calculated by the product of the average probability of illness per serving and the annual number of servings defined by the

user.

The risk assessment module of *Growth Predictor* enables also the assessment of the impact of partitioning (fractionation), mixing and increase in prevalence and microbial load due to cross-contamination at the food chain compartments “end of processing to retail”, “Retail” (e.g., due to slicing or mixing) and “Domestic environment” (e.g., due to food preparation), on the final estimation of ingested dose, the probability of illness per serving, and the total number of cases per annum. The estimation of changes in microbial contamination in the context of the above process are described in the following paragraphs:

Partitioning: By selecting “Partitioning” the user needs to define the partition coefficient (PP) by assigning a value from >0 (almost elimination of the batch) to 1 (no partitioning). For instance, a value of 0.5 suggests that the batch is divided in half. This apparently affects the distribution of microbial contamination in the sub-products resulting from the partitioning. The user is requested to also introduce the mass ($mass$) of the product that is partitioned. As such, if the product carries N_0 CFU/g prior to partitioning, then the population in the sub-products generated by partition follows a binomial distribution: $\text{Binomial}(N_0 * mass, PP)$. The same concept applies to all consecutive modules, where partition is applied.

Mixing: Clicking on “Mixing” allows the user to define the initial mass (in g: 0 to infinity), i.e., the mass of the incoming product at a particular stage and the added mass, i.e., the mass of the product mixed with the incoming batch. A value of 0 for any of the two variables means that no product is added in the mixture, associated with the relevant mass part.

Probability of cross contamination: this is a continuous value between 0 and 1 that informs the algorithm about the increase in the prevalence at that stage (i.e., it refers to newly contaminated packages), due to cross-contamination. In particular, if the initial prevalence is P , then a cross contamination probability P_{cc} will lead to a new prevalence (P_{new}), increased by the following amount: $P_{new} = P + (1-P)P_{cc}$. Apparently, if the additional contamination only affects the already contaminated packages, then P_{cc} equals to 0 and the introduced contamination $\text{Log} \frac{CFU_B}{g}$ simply increases the microbial load of the already contaminated products.

When mixing an incoming product of $mass A$, and microbial population density of $\text{Log} \frac{CFU_A}{g}$, with a new product of $mass B$ that also contributes with an additional contamination of $\text{Log} \frac{CFU_B}{g}$, the microbial concentration of the resulting mixture ($\text{Log CFU}_{mix}/g$; herein “Log” refers to \log_{10}) is estimated as follows:

$$\text{Log} \frac{CFU_{mix}}{g} = \text{Log} \left(\frac{CFU_A/g}{\frac{mass_A + mass_B}{mass_A}} + \frac{CFU_B/g}{\frac{mass_A + mass_B}{mass_B}} \right) \quad (27)$$

taking into account the dilution of the microbial concentration of the incoming product ($mass A$) due to mixing with the additional mass ($mass B$), plus the microbial contamination coming from product B. The microbial concentration in the new product mass ($mass B$) is also diluted by mixing with the incoming batch. As such, the concentration of the hazard coming from mass B, in the mixture becomes:

$$\text{Log} \frac{CFU_B}{g} = \text{Log} \frac{CFU_B/g}{\frac{mass_A + mass_B}{mass_B}} \quad (28)$$

Furthermore, to account for both situations, where the incoming product is free of microbial contamination ($\text{Log} \frac{CFU_A}{g} = 0$), or carries a microbial load, i.e., $\text{Log} \frac{CFU_A}{g} \neq 0$, the concentration of the microbial hazard in the mixture is assumed to follow a *Uniform* distribution:

Table 5

Input of variables and outputs of exposure assessment and risk metrics in representative examples of QMRA for three hypothetical scenarios of *Listeria monocytogenes* in meat.

Input variables	Modules											
	Farm to end of processing			End of processing to retail			Retail			Domestic environment		
	Baseline scenario	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Baseline scenario	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Baseline scenario	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Baseline scenario	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
Initial prevalence ^a	0.1	0.05	0.01									
Initial contamination (Log CFU/g)	2.6	Normal (2.6, 0.68)	Normal (1.3, 0.68)									
Time (d) ^b	na ^c	0.2	0.2	3	3	3	9	Expon (10, 30)	Expon (8, 30)	Pert (5,8,13)	Pert (5,8,13)	Pert (3,6,10)
Temperature (°C)	na	7	7	7	7	7	7	Normal (7, 1)	Normal (7, 1)	Normal (8,0.5)	Normal (8,0.5)	Normal (6,0.5)
Partitioning (p) ^d				No	No	No	No	0.1	0.01	No	No	No
Initial mass (g) ^e							na	1000	1000	na	na	na
Mixing ^f				No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Mass A				-	-	-	-	-	-	25	25	25
Mass B				-	-	-	-	-	-	100	100	100
Probability of cross contamination (P _{cc}) ^g				0	0	0	0.2	0.1	0.05	0	0	0
Level of newly introduced contamination Log CFU/g of mass B				0	0	0	Pert (0.8,1.5,2.1)	Pert (0.8,1.5,2.1)	Pert (0.3,0.7,1.1)	0.5	0.2	0
Product characteristics												
pH	na	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)	Normal (6,0.12)
a _w	na	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970	0.970
Inhibitor 1 (e.g., nitrites)	na	50	100	50	50	100	50	50	100	50	50	100
Growth estimation ^h												
a) Fixed value (Log change)	Normal (1,0.5)	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected	Not selected
b) With growth model	Not selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected	Selected
Model with interactions	na	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Microbial characteristics ⁱ												
N _{max} (Log CFU/g)	na	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
h ₀	na	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)	0.01 (no lag)
μ _{ref} (hr ⁻¹)	na	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.419
T _{ref} (°C)	na	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
T _{min} (°C)	na	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83	-2.83
pH _{min}	na	4.4	4.4	4.97	4.97	4.4	4.97	4.97	4.4	4.97	4.97	4.4
α _{amin}	na	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923
MIC (ppm)	na	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Reduction due to processing (log units) ^j	Pert (0.4,1.5,3.2)	Pert (0,0.2,1.2)	Pert (0,0.2,1.2)									
Cooking conditions												
Cooking temperature (°C)										No cooking	68	68
Cooking time (min)										No cooking	0.5	0.5
T _{ref}										-	57.8 ^k	57.8
D _{ref}										-	10	10
Z										-	6.5	6.5
Serving size (g)										Gamma (4.76,12.84)	Gamma (4.76,12.84)	Gamma (4.76,12.84)
Dose response model										Exponential (r = 8.39e-12) <i>L. monocytogenes</i> : susceptible population		

- ^a The shaded areas throughout table suggest that the annotated variable is non-applicable at this module and cannot receive any input.
- ^b For the first module, time and temperature as well as product characteristics are relevant on a case-by-case basis: for instance, they may be critical in a handling/packaging plant, where the product is not processed, and thus, the growth of the initial contamination at this module indeed depends on time and temperature. On the other hand, when processing takes place leading to a new formulation, time and temperature during processing are not relevant, neither are the product characteristics before the end of processing. The impact of these variables at this stage needs to be omitted from the simulations, by selecting “Growth estimation” as “fixed value” set at 0.
- ^c Non applicable.
- ^d When there is no partitioning (default status), the value for partition coefficient (PP) is 1 (whole product).
- ^e It refers to the mass of the product to be partitioned, to enable the estimation of the concentration of the microorganism in the resulting parts. When no partitioning is applied (default status), this mass equals 1 g.
- ^f In the absence of mixing (default status), *Mass A* = 1 g and *Mass B* = 0 g.
- ^g When there is no cross-contamination (default status), *P_{cc}* = 0.
- ^h When “Growth estimation by fixed value” is selected, the user is requested to enter, deterministically, or stochastically, the log increase, either as positive (growth) or negative (reduction) value. Upon selection of this option, product characteristics and model parameters are temporarily non relevant. They become relevant again when selecting growth estimation “With growth model”. Exceptionally, in the first module, log reductions are not eligible through “Growth estimation by fixed value” and should be defined only through the option “Reduction by processing”, further down.
- ⁱ The default cardinal values are those for *L. monocytogenes* in Food Spoilage and Safety Predictor (FSSP: <http://fssp.food.dtu.dk/>).
- ^j Applicable only for the very first module, reflecting the impact of lethal treatment on the raw materials entering the processing plant and bearing the initial contamination levels, as defined in the relevant field on top of the table.
- ^k Approximate thermal resistance properties of *L. monocytogenes* based on Doyle et al. (2001).

Table 6
Exposure and risk outputs of simulations based on the inputs of Table 5.

Metrics	Baseline scenario		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
	Growth Predictor ^a	@Risk 8.0 ^b	Growth Predictor	@Risk 8.0	Growth Predictor	@Risk 8.0
<i>Exposure metrics</i>						
Mean dose of exposure	8.0	7.53	6.2	5.68–5.69	2.8–2.9	2.40
<i>P</i> _{5%}	6.71–6.74	6.07–6.09	3.87–3.92	3.26–3.32	1.20–1.26	0.85–0.90
<i>P</i> _{50%}	7.95–7.97	7.51–7.52	6.03–6.09	5.48–5.52	2.50–2.60	2.16–2.17
<i>P</i> _{95%}	9.38–9.4	8.99–9.05	8.51–8.53	8.42–8.43	5.16–5.60	4.71–4.78
<i>Risk metrics</i>						
Mean Probability per serving	2.26–2.34e-04	7.88–7.92e-05	1.98–2.13e-06	5.80–5.96e-07	3.10–3.60e-10	1.22e-10
<i>P</i> _{5%}	1.22–1.28e-05	2.78–2.91e-06	8.92e-09-1.00e-08	2.19–2.55e-09	7.99–8.99e-12	3.00–3.49e-12
<i>P</i> _{50%}	2.10–2.21e-04	7.64–7.75e-05	1.31–1.51e-06	3.65–4.02e-07	1.56–2.00e-10	7.14–7.44e-11
<i>P</i> _{95%}	5.55–5.82e-03	2.36–2.60e-03	3.96–4.09e-04	3.22–3.30e-04	7.21e-08-1.55e-07	2.55–3.02e-08

^a : Range represents the result of multiple samplings (simulations) from the stochastic variables, for 10.000 iterations each.
^b : Range represents the result of multiple samplings (simulations) from the stochastic variables, for 10.000 iterations each.

$$\text{Log} \frac{CFU_{mix}}{g} \sim \text{Log} \left\{ \text{Uniform} \left[\min \left(\frac{CFU_A}{g}, \frac{CFU_B}{g} \right), \max \left(\frac{CFU_{mix}}{g}, \frac{CFU_B}{g} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (29)$$

The tool can be used to assess the consumer exposure to pathogens, the probability of illness *per* serving and the expected number of annual cases for a user-defined total number of eating events (servings) (Fig. 9). Furthermore, the direct on line update of exposure and risk estimates for every single change of the risk model inputs, enables the comparative assessment of alternative “what if” scenarios and thus, their relative risk ranking. For instance, the impact of some variability distributions that have not yet been embedded in the model, such as the cumulative distribution, may be approximated by testing the immediate effect of different (discrete) values of these distribution as deterministic inputs in the simulation.

In the examples of Table 5, three example scenarios were tested for varying product characteristics considering different initial contamination levels, partition and cross-contamination at retail, mixing at domestic environment and variability in the serving size with or without cooking. The hazard considered in these (theoretical) QMRA exercises is *L. monocytogenes*. This information is inserted into the tool through the cardinal values for growth, which were those used in Food Spoilage and Safety Predictor (FSSP; <http://fssp.food.dtu.dk/>), for this particular microorganism. In the same context, the exponential dose response model for exposure of susceptible individuals to *L. monocytogenes* with

an *r* value of 8.39e-12 was applied (FAO/WHO, 2004; Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2017). The first scenario represents the worst case, due to the high initial contamination, the most favorable growth characteristics and the lack of cooking. It is considered the baseline scenario, with a maximum average probability of illness *per* serving from 2.07 to 2.10e-04. The other 2 are scenarios involve mitigation actions that lead to reduction of the average probability of illness *per* serving compared to the baseline scenario. In each of these additional scenarios, extra features are also used compared to the first one, such as partitioning at retail (in both scenarios 2 and 3) and mixing at domestic level (only in scenario 3). ‘Partitioning’ simulates slicing, chopping or grinding of a large product, here in 1000 g to pieces of 10 or 100 g, due to fractionation of product by 1 (*PP* = 0.1) and 10 % (*PP* = 0.01), respectively. ‘Mixing’ resembles the mix, before cooking, of the product reaching that stage with a new mass of product, herein at a ratio 1:4, that is also contaminated (first 2 scenarios) or not (scenario 3). Moving from the baseline to the 3rd scenario, partition coefficient increases, whereas prevalence and re-contamination decrease. The growth characteristics of the baseline and scenario 2 are the same and the rest of the input variables are of similar magnitude, except for the time at retail, which is only 9 days at the baseline scenario, whereas in the second scenario, it follows exponential distribution with a mean value of 10 days and a maximum value of 30. The most impactful difference on the probability of illness is the absence of cooking in the baseline scenario. As a result the mean

exposure dose of scenario 2, where cooking is applied, is reduced by 2.5–3 logs compared to the baseline scenario, leading to a concomitant reduction in the average probability of illness of approximately 1000-fold. In scenarios 2 and 3, the same cooking intensity is applied, but scenario 3 represents better hygiene practices, i.e., less cross- and re-contamination, shorter storage times at retail and domestic environment, and lower temperature at home. These improvements collectively lead to reduction of exposure dose in scenario 3 by 2.6–2.7 compared to the scenario 2 and 1000-fold decrease in the average probability of illness per serving. Due to the high frequency of extremely low exposure levels in scenario 2, the calculation of the average could be sometimes erroneous and might require testing different number of iterations or resetting any of the stochastic input variables and re-running the model. The outputs of *Growth Predictor* were benchmarked with *@Risk* version 8, according to the XL file “@Risk_Simulations_Table5.xlsx” of supplementary material (Table 6). The *@Risk* file encompasses the same calculations in all 4 modules as *Growth Predictor*. Both tools were run for 10,000 iterations, multiple times. Outputs of *@Risk* did not differ with the sampling method, i.e., Monte Carlo vs Latin Hypercube (results not shown). The mean, 5 %–95 % percentiles and median of the dose of exposure estimated by *Growth Predictor* were constantly higher than that estimated with *@Risk* by 0.3–0.6 log units and the metrics in probability of illness per serving assessed by *Growth Predictor* were on average 2.2 to 3.8-fold higher than *@Risk* (Table 6). The highest differences between the two applications were observed in the 5 % and 95 % percentiles of the 2 output distributions and the lowest in the 50 % percentiles. Furthermore, the lowest recorded differences were evident for the 3rd (best case) scenario. Such discrepancies may be possibly due to the differences between the 2 tools in the algorithm supporting the *Monte Carlo* simulation, which impacts the 5–95 % range of output distribution and thus, the remaining metrics. Overall, the result of the 2 applications are highly comparable, suggesting that the algorithm of *Growth Predictor* is reproducible by a benchmarked software.

This module primarily aims to enable the assessment, as realistically as possible, of the impact of different risk scenarios along the food chain on consumers risk, without being over-ambitious to resemble the thoroughness of all possible QMRAs. As such, some additional (complex) hypotheses, that could be possibly encompassed in QMRAs, such as additional sources of variability, some types of variability distributions (e.g., cumulative or beta, etc.), or uncertainty of the parameters of distributions that describe variability (as a second dimension of risk assessment), may not be accommodated by the tool at the moment. The systematic testing of the software in different QMRA exercises will identify the aforementioned limitations and will prompt the necessary adjustments or amendments of the tool, in order to enhance its completeness and comply with the needs of complex QMRA approaches.

10. Conclusions

The freeware presented here has been designed to offer holistic predictive microbiology utilities, including model fitting, growth simulations under static and dynamic conditions and QMRA. Growth simulations may be performed with deterministic or stochastic inputs of the key factors controlling microbial growth, i.e., temperature, pH, a_w and one (e.g., critical for the shelf-life) preservative. Founding the mathematics of the tool on gamma concept provides flexibility for testing different microorganism-food combinations, interoperability and easiness in translating the knowledge of growth limiting conditions of any microorganism into growth predictions or exposure assessment, under various scenarios occurring in the food supply chain and the domestic environment (e.g., handling, storage and cooking). An additional novel feature of this software is the ability to describe growth limiting values of intrinsic and extrinsic food properties as normal distributions, thereby also reflecting the strain-to-strain variability in growth simulations. The tool is intended to be used by various end-users from academia, research, regulatory authorities and the food industry, acquainted or

not, with the relevant predictive microbiology skills. Overall, it is foreseen as a user-friendly tool for testing the safety and stability of food formulations, the compliance with microbiological criteria and for making informed decisions about the public health impact of different food chain scenarios of various microorganism-food combinations. The ambition and ultimate goal is the systematic use of the freeware and its update with additional features, based on the feedback by the different potential users, in order to meet the variety of foreseeable and emerging needs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Panagiotis N. Skandamis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2025.116329>.

Data availability

The R code of the software tool is available upon request

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